

a “worm’s-eye view” (e.g., $ax^3 + bx^2 + cx$). Both a complex function and a combination of separated functions could form the same component of a model.

The second interpretive realm is the choice of physical object. With physical objects in the real world, we can realize the same function (e.g., addition) with diverse methods (e.g., record multiple sounds by using a microphone or mix different sound sources in a mixer). For the re-physicalization, we must consider the degree of abstraction as well as the practicability of physical objects.

3.2 2017 HANARART Implementation

In the 2017 HANARART art festival implementation, we re-physicalized Whirlwind in a room of Yagi Fudanotsuji Kouryuukan, an old cultural property in Nara, Japan.

Figure 2: An overview of Aphysical Unmodeling Instrument in HANARART2017.

Figure 3: Brock diagram of Aphysical Unmodeling Instrument

At first, we replaced the **envelope** with a paper windmill triggered by the wind. When the wind blew, the motor attached to the windmill converted the rotational energy of the paper windmill into voltage.

Noise was re-physicalized using a combination of a needle, a piezo microphone, and a paper belt running similar to a cassette tape. The microphone was attached to the end of the needle and perceived the scratching noise from the other end of the needle as an electric signal.

The **delays** were replaced with sound wave propagations. We employed three sets of speakers and microphones. The time delay changed according to the rotation of a bar with the speakers attached to the end of the bar. The pitch of the feedback sound changed because of the changes in the delay time.

We re-physicalized most of the **additions** as electrical additions with an audio mixer. As an exception, we employed acoustic additions with the two speakers and two micro-

phones of Delay1 and Delay2, as well as three speakers and a microphone of Delay3.

For the **multiplications**, we used a set of an LED and photoresistor (CdS cell) in the envelope. The CdS behaved as a volume controller by changing its resistance, whereas the brightness of the LED corresponded to the voltage of the envelope. We also replaced the multiplication in the polynomial $ax^3 + bx^2 + cx$ with two double-balanced mixer ICs because of the requirement of a fast response in the model (the LED and CdS were too slow for this purpose).

We replaced the **resonator** of a lip or a reed with paper cylinders. Each of the cylinders had a different length and diameter. They moved randomly between the speaker and the microphone as a result of the wind movement.

For the **one-pole (low-pass) filter**, we hung two pieces of paper in front of the two speakers on the bar to reflect and excise the high-frequency tone.

Through our examination of the model, we identified no purpose of the biquad filter at the final section. Therefore, we did not use that filter in our re-physicalization.

3.3 Results

According to the implementation, we noticed that the sound from the installation was more similar to a normal Larsen tone than to the sound from the original Whirlwind that we previously implemented on a computer. This may have been due to three errors that we noticed after the implementation. The first was the reverse order of the resonance and the nonlinearity. The second was the multiplication with the LED and the CdS for the envelope control instead of an addition in the proto-model of the trumpet. The third was the inappropriate use of the paper cylinder as a resonator in terms of its behavior. Because of its extremely low weight, the sound from the reflectance of the cylinder was too low to notice the effect of the resonance.

4. DISCUSSION

The Whirlwind model virtually combines three real wind instruments. Therefore, in the re-physicalization, we had to interpret the undescribed part of the model. With such interpretation, the work could take various forms in different environments, even if the model was identical.

In future work, we would like to correct the limitations identified in our results. We aim to extend our approach with other formats, such as sound sculptures or a performance with different interpretations.

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